

On 2-Word Representable Graphs

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ABSTRACT

A graph $G = (V; E)$ is representable if there exists a word W over the alphabet V such that letters x and y alternate in W if and only if $(x; y) \in E$ for each $x \neq y$. If W is k -uniform (each letter of W occurs exactly k times in it) then G is called k -representable. We prove that a graph is representable if and only if it is k -representable for some k . In this paper we present the word representation of the class of graphs which are having the representation number 2 using the word representation of path graph and cycle graph.

Key Words: Word-Representable graphs, Maximum Planar Graphs, X-Graph, Y-Graph, Fan Graphs, Windmill graphs, Friendship graphs.

1 Introduction

In this section we will discuss some basic definitions regarding words and graphs.

Definition 1.1: Let w be a word over some alphabets. The letters x and y alternate in w if after deleting all letters in w but the copies of x and y we either obtain a word $xyxy\dots$ (of even or odd length) or a word $yxyx\dots$ (of even or odd length).

Example 1.2: Let $w=23412314$ be the word then the letters 1 and 2 alternate while the letters 1 and 4 do not alternate.

Example 1.3: The graph of the word "INDIA" is given below.

Figure 1: Graph of word $w = INDIA$.

Definition 1.4: A word is k -uniform if each letter in w occurs k times.

Example 1.5: 12341234 is a 2-uniform word, while 1234 is a 1-uniform word.

Definition 1.6: A graph is k -word-representable or k -representable if there exists a k -uniform word representing it.

Definition 1.7: Graph's representation number is the least k such that the graph is k -representable.

Theorem 1.8: A Graph G is k -word representable then it is also $(k + 1)$ -representable.

Definition 1.9: An orientation of a graph is transitive if presence of edges uv and vw implies presence of the edge.

Definition 1.10: A graph G is permutationally representable if there is a word $w = p_1 p_2 \dots p_k$ such that w represents G and for every i , the word p_i is a permutation of the vertices of G . Then w is called permutation-representant, or k -permutation-representant. The smallest number of permutations needed to represent G is called the permutation-representation number.

Definition 1.11: The initial permutation of a word w is defined as first occurrence of every letter from w by removing all other occurrence.

Definition 1.12: The graph $Pl_n = (V, E)$, where $V = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $E = E(K_n) \setminus \{(k, l) : 3 \leq k \leq n - 2 \text{ and } k + 2 \leq l \leq n\}$ is a planar graph having maximum number of edges, with n vertices. The planar graph Pl_n having maximum

number of edges with n vertices is obtained by removal of $[(n - 4)(n - 3)]/2$ edges from K_n . The number of edges in $Pl_n : n \geq 5$ is $3(n - 2)$.

Definition 1.13: A fan graph $F_{m,n}$ is the graph defined as $F_{m,n} = \overline{K_m} + P_n$, where $\overline{K_m}$ is the empty graph on m vertices and P_n is the path graph on n vertices. If $m = 1$, it is the usual fan graph and if $m = 2$, then it is the double fan graph.

Definition 1.14: The Dutch windmill graph D_3^m (usual windmill graph), also called a friendship graph, is the graph obtained by taking copies of m the cycle graph C_3 with a vertex in common. Extend the definition to D_n^m consisting of copies of m the cycle graph C_n .

2 Word representation of Maximum Planar Graph, X-Graph, Y-graph, Fan graphs, Windmill graphs:

Theorem 2.1: $R_k(Pl_n) = 2$.

Proof: If $n \leq 4$ we need one copies of each vertex as $v_1 v_2 v_3 v_4$ form a complete graph. For $n > 4$, we need minimum two copies of each vertex to represent the graph. Since the path $v_3 v_4 v_5 \dots v_{n-1} v_n$ represented by the word $v_3 v_5 v_3 \dots v_n v_{n-1} v_n v_{n-1} \dots v_5 v_3 v_4$ [4] and every vertex of this path connected to the path v_1 & v_2 . Thus, the word representation of Pl_n is given by $v_1 v_2 v_3 v_5 v_3 \dots v_n v_{n-1} v_1 v_2 v_n v_{n-1} \dots v_5 v_3 v_4$

Thus, representation number $R_k(Pl_n) = 2$.

Figure 2: Maximum Planar Graph

Theorem 2.2: $R_k(X - graph) = 2$.

Proof: Since there are two paths $x_1 x_2 x_3 \dots x_i x_{i+1} \dots x_n$ and $y_1 y_2 y_3 \dots y_j y_{j+1} \dots y_m$. Let us assume that $x_i = y_j$ is the intersection point. Since the representation number of path graph is 2. Therefore, word representation of the path $x_1 x_2 x_3 \dots x_i x_{i+1} \dots x_n$ contains two copies of x_i and the word of the form $w = x_1 x_2 x_1 x_3 x_2 x_4 x_3 \dots x_i \dots x_i \dots x_n$. Now we include the vertices of the path $y_1 y_2 y_3 \dots y_j y_{j+1} \dots y_m$ to w without affecting w . The following illustration given the 2-representation of $X - graph$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 w &= x_1 x_2 x_1 x_3 x_2 x_4 x_3 \dots x_i \dots x_i \dots x_n \\
 &= x_1 x_2 x_1 x_3 x_2 x_4 x_3 \dots y_{j-1} x_i y_{j-1} \dots y_{j+1} x_i y_{j+1} \dots x_n. \text{ (Since } x_i = y_j \text{)} \\
 &= x_1 x_2 x_1 x_3 x_2 x_4 x_3 \dots y_{j-2} y_{j-1} y_{j-2} x_i y_{j-1} \dots y_{j+1} x_i y_{j+2} y_{j+1} y_{j+2} \dots x_n \\
 &= x_1 x_2 x_1 x_3 x_2 x_4 x_3 \dots y_{j-3} y_{j-2} y_{j-3} y_{j-1} y_{j-2} x_i y_{j-1} \dots y_{j+1} x_i y_{j+2} y_{j+1} y_{j+3} y_{j+2} y_{j+3} \dots x_n \\
 &= x_1 x_2 x_1 x_3 x_2 x_4 x_3 \dots y_1 y_2 y_1 \dots y_{j-3} y_{j-2} y_{j-3} y_{j-1} y_{j-2} x_i y_{j-1} \dots y_{j+1} x_i y_{j+2} y_{j+1} y_{j+3} y_{j+2} y_{j+3} \dots y_m y_{m-1} y_m \dots x_n.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence $R_k(X - graph) = 2$.

Figure 3: X-Graph

Theorem 2.3: $R_k(Y - graph) = 2$.

Proof: Since there are two paths $x_1x_2x_3 \dots x_ix_{i+1} \dots x_n$ and $y_1y_2y_3 \dots y_m$. Let us assume that $x_i = y_m$ is the intersection point. Then the derivation of word is given from the following steps.

Since the representation number of path graph is 2. Therefore, word representation of the path $x_1x_2x_3 \dots x_ix_{i+1} \dots x_n$ contains two x_i and the word of the form $w = x_1x_2x_3x_4x_3 \dots x_i \dots x_i \dots x_n$. Now we include the vertices of the path $y_1y_2y_3 \dots y_m$ to w without affecting w . The following illustration given the 2-representation of $X - graph$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 w &= x_1x_2x_1x_3x_2x_4x_3 \dots y_mx_iy_m \dots x_i \dots x_n \\
 &= x_1x_2x_1x_3x_2x_4x_3 \dots y_{m-1}y_my_{m-1}x_iy_m \dots x_i \dots x_n. \text{ (Since } x_i = y_j \text{)} \\
 &= x_1x_2x_1x_3x_2x_4x_3 \dots y_{m-2}y_{m-1}y_{m-2}y_my_{m-1}x_iy_m \dots x_i \dots x_n \\
 &= x_1x_2x_1x_3x_2x_4x_3 \dots y_1y_2y_1 \dots y_{m-2}y_{m-1}y_{m-2}y_my_{m-1}x_iy_m \dots x_i \dots x_n
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence $R_k(Y - graph) = 2$.

Figure 4: Y-Graph

Theorem 2.4: $R_k(F_{m,n}) = 2, m \neq 1, n \neq 2.$

Proof:

Since $F_{1,2}$ is complete graph of 3 vertices. The word of $F_{1,2}$ is simply $x_1 a_1 a_2$. The path $a_1 a_2 a_3 \dots a_n$ is represented by $a_1 a_3 a_2 \dots a_n a_{n-1} a_n a_{n-1} \dots a_3 a_1 a_2$ [4]. Therefore, the word of $F_{1,n}$ is $x_1 a_1 a_3 a_2 \dots a_n a_{n-1} x_1 a_n a_{n-1} \dots a_3 a_1 a_2$.

Since the empty graph on two vertices $x_1 x_2$ is $x_1 x_2 x_2 x_1$. Therefore, the word of $F_{2,n}$ is $x_1 x_2 a_1 a_3 a_2 \dots a_n a_{n-1} x_2 x_1 a_n a_{n-1} \dots a_3 a_1 a_2$.

Since the empty graph on two vertices $x_1 x_2 x_3$ is $x_1 x_2 x_3 x_3 x_2 x_1$. Therefore, the word of $F_{3,n}$ is $x_1 x_2 x_3 a_1 a_3 a_2 \dots a_n a_{n-1} x_3 x_2 x_1 a_n a_{n-1} \dots a_3 a_1 a_2$. Continue in this way we get the word of $F_{m,n}$ is,

$x_1 x_2 x_3 \dots x_{m-1} x_m a_1 a_3 a_2 \dots a_n a_{n-1} x_m x_{m-1} \dots x_3 x_2 x_1 a_n a_{n-1} \dots a_3 a_1 a_2$.

Hence, $R_k(F_{m,n}) = 2, m \neq 1, n \neq 2.$

Figure 5: Fan-Graphs

Theorem 2.5: $R_k(D_3^m) = 2.$

Proof: The word representation of Dutch windmill graph is given by the following table. From the table, $R_k(D_3^m) = 2.$

Graph	Representation
D_3^2	$x a_1 a_2 a_3 a_4 x a_3 a_4 a_1 a_2$
D_3^3	$x a_1 a_2 a_3 a_4 a_5 a_6 x a_5 a_6 a_3 a_4 a_1 a_2$
D_3^4	$x a_1 a_2 a_3 a_4 a_5 a_6 a_7 a_8 x a_7 a_8 a_5 a_6 a_3 a_4 a_1 a_2$
D_3^m	$x a_1 a_2 a_3 a_4 a_5 a_6 \dots a_{m-1} a_m x a_{m-1} a_m \dots a_5 a_6 a_3 a_4 a_1 a_2$

Figure 6: Usual Windmill Graphs D_3^m

Theorem 2.5: $R_k(D_n^2) = 2$.

Proof: The word representation of Dutch windmill graph is given by the following table. From the table, $R_k(D_n^2) = 2$.

Graph	Representation
D_4^2	$xa_3a_1a_5a_4a_6a_5xa_6a_4a_2a_1a_3a_2$
D_5^2	$xa_4a_1a_6a_5a_7a_6a_8a_7xa_8a_5a_2a_1a_3a_2a_4a_3$
D_6^2	$xa_1a_5a_7a_6a_8a_7a_9a_8a_{10}a_9xa_{10}a_6a_2a_1a_3a_2a_4a_3a_5a_4$

Figure 7: Windmill Graph D_n^2 .

Conclusion:

In this paper we derived the word representation of some 2-word representable graphs. The words are derived using the words of path graphs and cycle graphs. Here, we conclude that the representation number of Maximum Planar Graphs, X-Graph, Y-Graph, Fan Graphs, Windmill graphs is 2.

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